

Title	Second report with feedback from users and statistics on use of the services
Work package n°	10
Deliverable n°	D10.2
Lead beneficiary	NILU
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Deliverable Type	R
Dissemination Level	PU
Estimated delivery date	30 th of September 2024
Actual delivery date	24 February 2025
Version	V2 (updated on 17.03.26)
Reviewed by	Cathrine Lund Myhre (NILU), Ariane Dubost (Project Office)
Accepted by	
Comments	V2: Following the final external review, the deliverable was corrected according to the recommendations.

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1 Summary and highlights

The user statistics and feedback from this period provide valuable insights into the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access (VA) Portal and its associated services. The VA Portal remains the primary entry point, with steady visits and positive satisfaction. Continued promotion will help expand its reach further.

The Homeless Data Portal continues to handle extensive submissions, underscoring its value in curating "homeless data". With 162 dataset DOIs coined and the number of unique user requests now reaching 18 (previously 12 in D10.1, +55%). Notably, no cross-RI dataset collections have been requested so far, suggesting that datasets tend to align with a single RI. Usability has been enhanced through the addition of a comprehensive FAQ section and collection DOI options. Future efforts will focus on outreach to attract a broader user base and encourage more submissions.

The Time Series Analysis Service has experienced strong growth in the number of accesses over time and dataset requests, reflecting significant user interest. Recent usability improvements, including interface enhancements and improved search functionality, were well received. Further refinements, particularly to ergonomics and filtering processes, are planned to make the service even more intuitive, and more data from ACTRIS DC will be added.

The Footprint Analysis Services continue to show high demand across ACTRIS, ICOS, and IAGOS, reinforcing their critical role for users to interpret the observations and plan actions and campaigns using forecasts. The ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service remains a key resource, with user requests for FLEXPART products now reaching 95 (previously 58 in D10.1, +64%). Updates such as improved documentation, download scripts, and enhanced mapping functionality have been implemented, while pending developments, including integration into the ACTRIS Data Portal, API indexing for large-scale downloads, and additional training resources, remain priorities. The ICOS Footprint Analysis Service has demonstrated robust user engagement, with over a thousand model runs and significant result downloads. New features, including CH₄ concentration calculations, expanded observational data coverage and improved station selection, address earlier feedback. Ongoing improvements will focus on result traceability and clearer guidance for scientific acknowledgment. The IAGOS Footprint Analysis Service has experienced steady growth, now displaying 8,643 footprints (previously 7,448 in D10.1, +16%) This growth is attributed to key enhancements, including an upgraded emission inventory, time-range filters, and a comprehensive user guide. These updates have improved precision and usability, contributing to increased visits and requests. Further efforts will aim to simplify the user interface for an even smoother experience.

Overall, user feedback indicates satisfaction with all services, though limited participation in the general feedback form highlights the need for targeted engagement and outreach. Moving forward, priority will be given to implementing pending updates, enhancing technical features, expanding training resources, and promoting services more widely. The final report will assess the impact of these refinements on user satisfaction and engagement.

2 Introduction

This report gives an overview of feedback from users and the statistics on use of the services offered within the Virtual Access (VA) Portal within ATMO-ACCESS for the period from launch until the 1st of November 2024. The VA Portal (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/>) gives access to several online services: the ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>), the Time Series Analysis (<https://services.iagos-data.fr/atmo-access/timeseries>) and three different Trajectory and Footprint analysis tools (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/#/footprint-services>). Each of the Research Infrastructures (RIs) in ATMO-ACCESS are responsible for different trajectory and footprint services depending on components and observation platforms, namely Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS). Massive Open Online Course (MOOC) on atmospheric observations in European research infrastructures is scheduled to be available by January 2025.

Usage statistics in this report are based on defined service-specific metrics to ensure transparency and consistency across reporting periods. As different services apply different counting methods, a dedicated Metrics chapter provides formal definitions and explains how usage figures should be interpreted.

Feedback is given by user panels, internal feedback, e-mails, discussions at meetings and a general feedback form. User panels consist of a small group of selected central users and groups within the RIs that comment on the service in dedicated meetings. The general feedback form is a form available at <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/>. The general feedback form has been updated since last feedback period, and thus only includes new feedback. Furthermore, the form has been made visible on the VA portal and all services and been sent out to users that have agreed to share their e-mail address.

3 Usage metrics

This chapter defines the usage metrics applied throughout the report to ensure transparent and consistent interpretation across services.

Visits are recorded when a user enters a webpage or performs a tracked action; a new visit is counted after 30 minutes of inactivity. Visits and unique visits are tracked using IP addresses and therefore represent an approximation of user activity rather than exact individual counts. Shared institutional IP addresses may represent multiple users, while dynamic IP addresses may generate multiple counts for the same user. The metric is primarily intended to monitor trends over time rather than exact user numbers. Requests represent service-specific user actions (e.g., data curation requests, model runs, or dataset access) and therefore differ between services. As definitions and denominators vary, metrics are not directly comparable across services. Detailed definitions and counting rules are provided in the tables below.

Visits	A session recorded when a user enters a webpage or performs an action, reset after 30 minutes of inactivity.
Unique visits	Visits identified by unique IP addresses (IP-based counting; not a one-to-one representation of individual persons).
VA portal entries	Button clicks from the VA portal to individual services (entry count, not confirmed service usage).
Requests	A service-specific action (e.g., data curation request, model run, dataset selection via API, or footprint display), depending on the service.
Dataset accessed	Dataset selected in Step "Select datasets" via RI APIs in the Time Series Analysis service.
Dataset curated / DOI coined	A dataset fully processed by an RI and assigned a DOI or PID.
Model run	A user-initiated STILT or FLEXPART calculation for a defined location and time range.
Download	Packaged model results downloaded by a user.
Footprint animation/view	A footprint displayed for a selected station and time period in the viewer interface.
Footprint day	One simulated day consisting of eight 3-hourly footprints.

Table 1: Overview and definitions of usage metrics used for reporting Virtual Access services.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
VA portal	Visits	Total page views of the VA portal	Includes repeated visits by same IP
	Unique visits	Unique page views based on IP addresses	IP-based; internal/external not distinguished

	VA portal entries	Button clicks to individual services	Counts entries, not confirmed use
Homeless Data Portal	Visits	Visits to the Homeless Data Portal webpage	IP-based
	Requests	Unique data curation issues submitted	Multiple datasets may belong to one request
	Dataset curated / DOI coined	Datasets processed and assigned DOI/PIDs	One request may include multiple datasets
Time Series Analysis	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to service	IP-based
	Dataset accessed	Datasets selected via RI APIs	1 request = 1 dataset access
ACTRIS Footprint analysis service	Visits	Visits to web interface	IP-based
	Requests	FLEXPART model run requests via form	Tracked in Redmine
ICOS Footprint analysis service	Footprint animation/view	Footprint animation displayed in the STILT results viewer	Counter per display event; each view includes up to one year of footprints
	Model run	STILT model runs started	1 run may cover multiple days
	Downloads	Model results downloaded	1 download may include multiple days
	Footprint day	Simulated footprint days generated	1 day = 8 footprints
IAGOS Footprint	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to viewer	IP-based
	Requests	Footprints displayed in viewer	Counted per display event

Table 2: Overview of usage metrics applied per Virtual Access service, including counting rules and limitations.

4 Virtual Access Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal provides access to all online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project.

ATMO ACCESS Home Contacts Documentation ATMO-CONNECT
PROJECT ACCESS FACILITIES EVENTS & OUTREACH NEW CALLS ALERT!

rtual Access Tool

ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal

This portal provides you with access to the new online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project. This include access to:

- Homeless data portal:**
A portal for submission of measurement data from research projects, not associated to any long-term projects/networks nor sustainable data centres.
- Footprint analysis tool for greenhouse gases, aerosols, reactive trace gases:**
Model tools for interpretation of measurement data both measured at the ground and from aircrafts. You can request model runs to produce data products (e.g footprint, source contributions) for your decided locations, or search and use the already produced products.
- Time series analysis:**
Identify, utilize and combine data more effectively across RIs and data repositories, including data coverage, collocation of data and visualisation of data.
- Massive open online course (MOOC)**
Online course 'Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the future of our atmosphere'. – Starting date: January 20, 2025 - Registrations from December 2, 2024

[LOGIN](#)

i You need to register to get access to the services. These services offered by ATMO-ACCESS are pilots for improvement over the project period. Accordingly, we need registration of users to get feedback and access statistic of the various services to meet the project requirements and increase the possibility of more funding for further development. When we collect personal data (e-mail) it is only for making it possible to contact you by e-mail. The information will be stored maximum 6 months after project completion, and you will only be contacted to provide feedback.

Figure 1: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal (link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>)

When using the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, the user is required to log in, as seen in Figure 1. This is to gain statistics for the project, and to collect feedback on the services developed. Figure 2 shows the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal after login, with buttons giving access to “Data curation of homeless data”, “Trajectory and footprint analysis”, “Tools for analysing time series” and “Online training service” (not yet available). The “Trajectory and footprint analysis” service includes one tool for each RI, which is Greenhouse Gases (ICOS), Tropospheric vertical gradients (IAGOS) and Aerosol distribution and source analysis (ACTRIS).

Lise Eder_Murberg

GIVE FEEDBACK

ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal

This portal provides you with access to the new online services developed in the ATMO-ACCESS project. This include access to:

- **Homeless data portal:**
A portal for submission of measurement data from research projects, not associated to any long-term projects/networks nor sustainable data centres.
- **Footprint analysis tool for greenhouse gases, aerosols, reactive trace gases:**
Model tools for interpretation of measurement data both measured at the ground and from aircrafts. You can request model runs to produce data products (e.g footprint, source contributions) for your decided locations, or search and use the already produced products.
- **Time series analysis:**
Identify, utilize and combine data more effectively across RIs and data repositories, including data coverage, collocation of data and visualisation of data.
- **Massive open online course (MOOC)**
Online course 'Atmospheric Research Infrastructures: Sharing the future of our atmosphere'. - Starting date: January 20, 2025 - Registrations from December 2, 2024

Data curation of homeless data

Trajectory and footprint analysis

Tools for analysing time series

Online training service

Figure 2: ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal page after login, including a new "give feedback" button.

4.1 Updates since last feedback report

The Virtual Access Portal has been updated with a QR code that links directly to the portal, making it easier for people to access when promoting it in presentations at meetings, posters, flyers etc. Furthermore, when logged into the portal, the VA Portal now includes a "Give Feedback" button that directs users to the general feedback form.

4.2 Statistics on use of the online services

Statistics on the use of the ATMO-ACCESS online services are tracked in several ways.

- Visits to the ATMO-ACCESS VA entry website are tracked using Matomo¹. The number of visits/page views to the VA page (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access/>) is provided in subsection 4.2.1.
- Access to the different services through the VA portal is tracked by counting hits on the corresponding access buttons.
- Each service independently tracks its effective usage by recording specific interactions and activities performed by users. This may include metrics such as the number of datasets accessed, model runs completed, or data curation requests processed. These detailed records provide a deeper understanding of how the services are utilized beyond mere access counts.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
VA portal	Visits	Total page views of the VA portal	Includes repeated visits by same IP
	Unique visits	Unique page views based on IP addresses	IP-based; internal/external not distinguished
	VA portal entries	Button clicks to individual services	Counts entries, not confirmed use

Table 3: Overview of usage metrics for VA portal, including counting rules and limitations.

4.2.1 User activity on the VA portal

The VA Portal's usage is monitored alongside visits to the main ATMO-ACCESS project webpage (<https://www.atmo-access.eu/>). Activity on the VA portal web page is thus measured by using metrics such as 'page views' and 'unique page views' from the tracking system, with the latter determined by unique IP addresses. Furthermore, the users have to register with e-mail to the VA portal to access the services. One user in the VA portal can access several services.

Table 4 shows the number of registered users, overall page views and unique page views between 23rd March 2023 and 1st November 2024. Figure 3 and Figure 4 show the monthly VA portal unique page views and page views, respectively. Peaks in March and May 2023 are due to the announcements of new services to the VA portal. The high period between October – December 2023 correlates with ACTRIS Week 2023, Svalbard Science Conference and IAGOS Users' meetings, all places where the VA services have been promoted. Lastly the high peak in March - May 2024 corresponds with ATMO-ACCESS Annual Meeting of 2024 and the ACTRIS Science Conference.

¹ Matomo is an open-source web analytics tool (<https://matomo.org/>)

Registered users	276
Page views	2915
Unique page views	1814

Table 4: Overview of VA Portal page views and unique page views between 23rd March 2023 and 1st November 2024.

Figure 3: Monthly 'VA Portal' unique page views (until 1st of November 2024).

Figure 4: Monthly 'VA Portal' page views (until 1st of November 2024).

4.2.2 Service access via the VA portal

Access to the different services in the Virtual Access portal is tracked by counting hits on each of the entry buttons. Table 5 shows the entries to the different services.

Footprints (all 3 services)	941
Homeless data portal	236
Time series analysis	271

Table 5: Entries to the different services between 23rd March 2023 and 1st November 2024.

4.3 Feedback from the general feedback form

The general feedback form for ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Services can be found here: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access-feedback-form/> and in 11. Appendix. The form was updated on the 7th of October 2024 and has been added to the VA portal and several of the services on the same date. On the 12th of November the form was distributed by email to all

users that have logged into the VA portal during the last year, with a reminder to fill out the form by end of November. Actions to promote the form have been taken, despite that in the last period the feedback form got only 4 replies. The answers related to the Virtual Access Portal are compiled in this section, while the more specific answers applying to the different services are included in the chapters describing the feedback to these services.

The figures only take 4 answers into account, and it is uncertain whether this can be considered as representative of the use of the services. Figure 5 shows where the users responding to the form first heard about the online services within the ATMO-ACCESS project. Figure 6 shows that 1 respondent accessed the Time Series Analysis service, 2 respondents accessed Footprint - Aerosol distribution and source analysis and 1 respondent accessed Footprint - Greenhouse gases. Figure 7 shows an evaluation of the access to the online services from the Virtual Access Portal, where all answers are between “OK” and “Very satisfied”.

How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project?

4 svar

Figure 5: Answers to "How did you find out about the online services supported by the ATMO-ACCESS project?". 4 answers in total.

Service accessed If you have tried more than one of these, please complete the entire form once for each service you want to give feedback on.

4 svar

Figure 6: Answers to "Service accessed". 4 answers in total, where 1 respondent accessed the Time Series Analysis service, 2 respondents accessed Footprint - Aerosol distribution and source analysis and 1 respondent accessed Footprint - Greenhouse gases.

Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>

Figure 7: Answers to “Please evaluate the access to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>”. 4 answers in total for the two first statements, 3 answers for the last statement (only asked to people accessing the footprint services).

5 ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>) provides users with a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TransNational Access (TNA) activities that have so far not been included into any data management and data curation system. These data sets are referred to as “homeless data” as they are not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. The goal of the portal is to make more atmospheric data (collected during campaigns and via TNA) available to the end-user, as well as to provide benefits for data custodians², by tracking the access and use of their data and getting access to RI specific tools for curation.

Making the data accessible through a FAIR³ data centre is the most efficient way to ensure long-term curation and promote visibility and access to data by a large user community. This homeless data portal makes these data well documented for use and easily available for future use.

² The individual or organization that has accountability and responsibility for the data and ensures appropriate care and maintenance of the resource.

³ Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (<https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>)

All requests for data curation and archiving services will be handled by the relevant research infrastructures (RI), seamless for the users. The architecture of the portal is described in section 2 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

The starting page of the Homeless Data Portal is shown in Figure 8. The user gets information about the portal and available options: 1) To request data curation and archiving, 2) to access ATMO-ACCESS related data, and 3) to request general support. Both option 1) and 3) are request forms to be filled out by the user and these requests are tracked in a redmine⁴ issue tracker by data curators. As a new addition, the general feedback form is included as a button as the starting page as well as the “FAQ and support” page.

⁴ <https://www.redmine.org/>

ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

The Homeless data portal is a portal for data curation of atmospheric measurement data. The portal is set up to serve scientists producing atmospheric measurements and time series resulting from research campaigns and TNA activities that are normally not included into any data management and data curation system and activity. These data sets are "homeless data", not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centers. The goal of the portal is to make more data available to the end-user, as well as providing benefits for data collectors in terms of usage tracking and access to RI (Research Infrastructure) specific tools for curation and data access.

All request for data curation and archiving services will be handled by a relevant research infrastructure. You will be contacted by e-mail after your request.

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback form](#)

Data Archiving and Curation

Apply for data curation and archiving services through the atmospheric RIs

[Access Services](#)

Data Access

Search ATMO-ACCESS related data from TNA and campaign activities

[Search Data](#)

General Support

Send a request if you have questions regarding the data in ATMO-ACCESS

[Get Support](#)

Figure 8: ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal Starting page (link: <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>).

5.1 Updates since last feedback report

Since the last feedback report [D10.1 First report with feedback from users and statistics on use](#), significant progress has been made in addressing the feedback provided last period, with several updates implemented to enhance user experience and functionality. A new comprehensive Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) section has been introduced, making it easier for users to find answers to common queries. This addition is located in the support section of the Homeless Data Portal, as shown in Figure 9.

Virtual Access Feedback

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback form](#)

FAQ

Frequently Asked Questions about the ATMO-ACCESS Homeless Data Portal

What does "homeless data" refer to and who can use this service? ^
In the ATMO-ACCESS Project "homeless data" refers to data sets not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centers. This includes data sets from Transnational Access (TNA) activities, research campaigns and 'short-term' national or international research projects. Anyone with data which falls under the classification of "homeless data", as described above, can use the service.
Is the service free of charge? v
Will my data be associated with the term "homeless data"? v
Can I request curation for stations, instruments or methods not already in the RIS? v
What to expect from us after submitting a request? v
What is expected by me? v
Which research infrastructure (RI) should I expect to be contacted by? v
Are there any tools for formatting the data correctly? v
What benefits are there to using the Homeless Data Portal, compared to storing the data by myself? v
Will I get DOI(s) for my data set(s) and what is a collection DOI? v

Figure 9: FAQ and support page of The Homeless Data Portal.

Is this a collection of datasets?
<input type="text" value="Yes"/>
If it is a collection of datasets, do you wish us to provide a collection DOI?
<input type="text" value="No"/>

Figure 10: Newly added questions to the data curation request form, where the user can specify if the request is a collection of datasets and if the user wishes to have a collection DOI on the datasets.

Users now have the option to request collection DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) for submitted collections of datasets, as illustrated in Figure 10. To further streamline the collection of user insights, a feedback form has been prominently integrated on both the start page and the FAQ and support page, as seen in Figure 8 and Figure 9. Additionally, the portal has been actively promoted to the scientific community, with details provided in *D10.4 - Report on the suitability of the different services modalities taking into account finances, outreach and scientific impact*.

5.2 Statistics on use of the Homeless Data Portal

Statistics on the use of the Homeless Data Portal are tracked in several ways. Firstly, as number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then the number of visits to the Homeless Data Portal itself (<https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no>), and lastly as the number of requests made through the portal. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (entry through the Homeless Data Portal button, as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people entering directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. Requests in the Homeless Data Portal are logged in the issue tracker when a user submits a curation request for a data set or a collection of datasets through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Homeless Data Portal	Visits	Visits to the Homeless Data Portal webpage	IP-based
	Requests	Unique data curation issues submitted	Multiple datasets may belong to one request
	Dataset curated / DOI coined	Datasets processed and assigned DOI/PIDs	One request may include multiple datasets

Table 6: Overview of usage metrics for Homeless Data Portal, including counting rules and limitations.

5.2.1 Users' activity on the Homeless Data Portal

Use of the Homeless Data Portal is tracked using Matomo. In Figure 11, a map shows the distribution of the use of to the portal worldwide (408 visits) and in Europe (329 visits). The access numbers are higher than the metrics from the VA portal where the Homeless Data Portal button had 236 entries, showing that some users access the Homeless Data Portal directly and some users access through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal. Table 7 lists the countries using the Homeless Data Portal most, and the number of visits for each country. Several developers and curators working on the Homeless Data Portal are located in Norway and France, hence higher numbers for these countries are expected since Matomo only counts by IP addresses and does not differentiate between internal ATMO-ACCESS users and external users. Lastly Figure 12 shows the number of visits and actions per visit over time. Actions comprise, for instance, page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches.

Figure 11: User map showing on the left-hand side a total of 408 visits to the Homeless Data Portal worldwide and on the right-hand side 329 visits in Europe from 23.03.2023 - 01.11.2024.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	73
United States	60
France	50
Sweden	25
Italy	23
Netherlands	22
Spain	21
Greece	19
Finland	18
Germany	16

Table 7: Countries with the most visits to the Homeless Data Portal from 23.03.2023 - 01.11.2024.

Figure 12: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 23.03.2023 - 01.11.2024. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.2 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

5.2.2 Data requests through the Homeless Data Portal

Requests in the Homeless Data Portal are compiled in a redmine issue tracker after a user requests the curation service through <https://homeless-data-portal.nilu.no/request>. After a request shows up in the issue tracker, the data curators assign which RI the data set(s) are associated to, and the data set(s) follow the normal data curation workflow. Statistics on the user requests for the service can be found in Table 8. The table counts the total number of user requests, the number of unique requests (some have sent similar requests two or more times for the same set of data), and open and closed issues. Open issues may arise because the issue was recently received or because only part of a collection of datasets has been sent to the RI and curated, while additional datasets are still pending. This is reflected in the difference between the 'Number of requested data curation services' and the 'Number of datasets curated.' The 'Number of requested data curation services' is subject to change during the communication process and should therefore be considered as indicative. In contrast, the 'Number of datasets curated' refers to the number of files that have been fully curated by one of the RIs and assigned a DOI. Lastly, the Table 8 lists the project associations that have requested curation services and the RIs their request have been associated with.

Number of requests (unique)	22 (18)
Open issues in progress	10
Closed issues (unique)	12 (8)
Number of requested data curation services	~ 193
Number of datasets curated (and given DOIs)	162

Project associations	5 (ATMO-ACCESS TNA, RI-URBANS, WeBASOOP, ICOS, EMPIRE)
Number of requests associated to ACTRIS DC	20
Number of requests associated to IAGOS DC	0
Number of requests associated to ICOS carbon portal	2

Table 8: Statistics on requests through the Homeless Data Portal from launch to 13.12.2024.

5.3 Feedback from users on the Homeless Data Portal

Feedback on the service is provided through user panel meetings and e-mail. The end of the feedback period was in November 2024, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during December 2024 -January 2025. Furthermore, users of the homeless data portal (all users sending requests for data curation) were encouraged to fill in the general feedback form but no answer directly related to the Homeless Data Portal has been received.

5.3.1 User panel for Homeless Data Portal

User panels consist of meetings with a small group of selected users, and within the RIs that comment on the service. The second feedback meeting with the User Panel of the Homeless Data Portal took place on the 16th of April 2024.

Participants: Lise Eder Murberg, Yong Lin, Margareta Hellström Damien Boulanger, Ewan O'Conner, Peristera Paschou, Maria Tsihla, Noemi Perez, Alex Vermeulen, Kelly Voudouri, Ute Karsten

The User Panel made the following recommendations and comments as regards to the Homeless Data Portal, as gathered in the sentences below:

- There should be a link to the general feedback form at the top of the home page, to try to gather more feedback from users.
- Some of the ATMO-ACCESS TNA users used a lot of the "Other" fields when filling out the data curation request form on the data curation page. It should be investigated whether the form can be adapted to better meet user needs.
- It is recommended to include GDPR-compliant text regarding the information entered in the data curation form. Additionally, a clear policy should be established for the deletion or retention of this information after the project's conclusion.
- More than one instrument is allowed. However, only a single contact person can be listed at the top of the page. Consider allowing the option to include multiple contacts. - *It's possible to include multiple contacts to each dataset at a later phase. (Answer from data curation team)*

- Currently the Data Access page does not include the repository IAGOS and ICOS will store the homeless data in, but only their standard data portals. This data is managed by Aeris and should be included on the Data Access page, even though it's currently empty.
- Comment on the workflow: A request was sent by one team member, while a colleague submitted the data, and the workflow is ok.

6 Time Series Analysis

The Time Series Analysis service provides users with a tool to identify, use and combine data across RIs and data repositories. It aims at serving a large variety of users (students, academics, private or public organizations, NGOs, communities of projects, etc.) by providing a dedicated Virtual Research Environment (VRE) for facilitating their exploration of multiple in situ datasets with long time series of different variables. The service makes accessible the most commonly used basic metrics (e.g. means, percentiles) and statistical analysis (e.g. trends), as well as visualization tools to look at e.g. 2D or 3D scatter plots. The combination of different variables important for climate and air quality recorded by ACTRIS, IAGOS and ICOS allows users to explore relevant cross-cutting issues. An example of the search functionality for available variables of the Time Series Analysis service is shown in Figure 13.

The architecture of the service is described in section 4 of deliverable [D5.1 – Detailed requirements and \(non-\) technical specifications for all services based on the user consultations](#).

Time-series analysis

GIVE FEEDBACK

0. Information 1. Search datasets 2. Select datasets 3. Filter data 4. Data analysis

NEXT →

Figure 13: ATMO-ACCESS Time Series Analysis Search datasets page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-timeseries>).

6.1 Updates since last feedback report

Since the last feedback report, numerous suggestions expressed in the user feedback were implemented and resulted in the improvement of service:

- A detailed user guide is available. It makes a complete tour of the service's functionalities and features.
- A presentation of the map with RI's stations was greatly improved (co-located stations issue resolved, better map readability).
- Overall ergonomics and clarity of the user interface of the service was improved.

6.2 Statistics on use of the Time Series Analysis service

Statistics on the use of the Time Series Analysis are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of visits to the Time-series analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (clicks on the "Tools for analysing time series" button, as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the web-page itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people

routed through the VA portal. Each RI provides access to their datasets through a dedicated API that is requested by the service. The number of requests to the service is considered similar to the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs⁵. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “2. Select datasets” in the service, which is the step after “1. Search datasets” which is shown in Figure 13. The statistics are available from June 2023 until November 1st, 2024.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
Time Series Analysis	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to service	IP-based
	Dataset accessed	Datasets selected via RI APIs	1 request = 1 dataset access

Table 9: Overview of usage metrics for Time Series Analysis, including counting rules and limitations.

6.2.1 Usage metrics for the Time Series Analysis service

User visits to the Time Series Analysis give an indication about how many people are using the service. Figure 14 shows the number of unique visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 477 (previously 351 in D10.1, +36%) for the period from June 22, 2023, to November 1st, 2024, where the high peak at around 26th of September most likely is when the first user panel was held. Unique visits refer to visits made by unique IP addresses.

⁵ An application programming interface (API) is a way for two or more computer programs to communicate with each other. It is a type of software interface, offering a service to other pieces of software.

Time series service - Visits

Figure 14: Number of unique visits over time - Time series service from June 22, 2023 to November 1, 2024.

6.2.2 Data analysis requests in the Time Series Analysis Service

The number of requests is the number of datasets accessed through the RIs data access APIs. This means the number of datasets accessed in step “2. Select datasets” in the service. Figure 15 shows the number of API requests over time. The total number of requests for the time series service is 2,179 (previously 1,433 in D10.1, +52%) for the period June 22, 2023, to November 1, 2024. On average, 4.5 datasets were requested by each user.

Time series service - Requests

Figure 15: Number of requests over time – Time series service from June 22, 2023 to November 1, 2024.

6.3 Feedback from users on the Time Series Analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in two ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in November 2024, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during December 2024 – January 2025.

6.3.1 User panel for Time Series Analysis service

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the time-series analysis service took place in September 2023 and a second one in April 2024. General feedback about the main features of the service (filtering and analysis) was very positive. Remarks from the second panel concerned the ergonomics of the service (improve display name of the variables, simplify selection and filtering, etc.).

More details on the feedback are available in Milestone MS5.4 section 2: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf> and in Milestone MS5.5 section 'Time-series analysis service': <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content->

aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/07/MS21-Feedback-meeting-2-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf

6.3.2 Feedback form for the Time Series Analysis service

Figures 16 through 20 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the Time Series Analysis Service; however, it is important to note that the data in the figures is based on responses from a single user and therefore represents only one individual's perspective. In Figure 16, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses indicating "OK" and "Poor" ratings across various aspects, suggesting areas for improvement. Figure 17 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with a high rating provided. In Figure 18, the user indicated an equal preference for various training formats, including videos, e-learning, and a library of resources, demonstrating an interest in support materials. Figure 19 highlights the user's positive evaluation of the Time Series Analysis, and Figure 20 outlines the perceived benefits, such as time savings and immediate access to results. While these insights are valuable, they are limited in scope due to the single response.

Figure 16: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

Figure 17: Answer to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

Figure 18: Answer to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

Figure 19: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Figure 20: Answer to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

7 ACTRIS footprint analysis service for aerosol and trace gas measurements

The ACTRIS footprint analysis service provides model tools to users for the interpretation of ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations. The users can request model runs to produce data products (e.g., footprints, source contributions) for defined ground-based stations and products or search and use data products for existing locations. Footprint products are used to provide air mass origin information that helps understand the trajectory of the air masses and to analyse atmospheric observations. Source contribution products give modelled contributions to a variable from a given sector e.g., modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from residential and commercial sector. All products are generated using the FLEXPART (FLEXible PARTicle dispersion model) and include footprint analysis for air masses arriving at the station on a 3-hour time resolution for 20 days back in time, except for near-real-time (NRT) products which are for the last 3 days and include a 1-day forecast. Currently data products can be requested for the variables and categories described in Table 10.

Black carbon	Standard products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements at sites with long time series
Dust	Products for analysing dust events at various sites
Specialized black carbon	Tailored products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements from specific campaigns
Other	Tailored products for analysing land-use change, sulphate, CO and OC from specific campaigns
Microplastic	Tailored products for analysing microplastic (MP) measurements from specific campaigns
Near Real Time (NRT)	Footprint products to be used for analysing NRT data and 1 day forecast

Table 10: Current FLEXPART products available for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations.

The starting page of the ACTRIS Footprint analysis service is shown in Figure 21. A user of this service has different options:

- i) to request new model runs,
- ii) to access current products already produced within ATMO-ACCESS, and
- iii) to get general support, e.g., for in-depth interpretation.

“Available FLEXPART Footprint products” shows ACTRIS stations with already processed standard black carbon footprint and source contribution products for years between 2007-2022 (within ATMO-ACCESS). The “FLEXPART Station map” shows a map of all stations with available products, where the marker for each station is dependent on the categories in Table 10.

ATMO-ACCESS

FLEXPART products for ground based aerosol and trace gas observations

FLEXPART Model Run

Request access to FLEXPART model run

[Request Access](#)

FLEXPART Products and Information

Access FLEXPART products and descriptions

[Access Data](#)

General Support

Do you have questions regarding the FLEXPART products in ATMO-ACCESS?

[Get Support](#)

To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Feedback Form](#)

Overview of stations with FLEXPART products

- Black carbon:** Standard products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements at sites with long time series
- Dust:** Products for analysing dust events at various sites
- Specialized black carbon:** Tailored products for analysing black carbon (BC) measurements from specific campaigns
- Other:** Tailored products for analysing landuse change, sulfate, CO and OC from specific campaigns
- Microplastic:** Tailored products for analysing microplastic (MP) measurements from specific campaigns
- Near Real Time (NRT):** Footprint products to be used for analysing NRT data and 1 day forecast

Figure 21: Starting page for ATMO-ACCESS Footprint products for ground-based aerosol and trace gas observations (link: <https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>).

7.1 Updates since last feedback report

Since the last feedback report, the ACTRIS footprint analysis service has implemented several updates to improve its service and address compiled user concerns. The website now includes comprehensive documentation of the products, providing detailed descriptions of available products and parameters for selection. This is accessible on the “FLEXPART products” page, and seen for Black Carbon in Figure 22. Additionally, download scripts have been implemented to streamline and optimize data transfer processes for users requesting to download all data from the website. The mapping feature has been improved to now offer a clear overview of available products and making it easier for users to locate and utilize relevant products. The map also started using the names of the locations, and not just the previous EBAS ID codes. These updates aim to enhance usability and accessibility across the webpage. Lastly the service is updated with several new locations with products, this in accordance with the requests received through the portal in this period.

Pending updates include the development of an API to facilitate large-scale machine-to-machine data downloads, matching of observations with modelled concentrations, and possibly the creation of a training video for the products. These suggestions are recognized as important and are being considered for implementation during the final feedback period, aligning with the service's long-term strategic goals. This requires support from other projects for full implementation, and need to align with timeline.

Black Carbon Organic Carbon Dust Microplastic NRT Sulfate and Landuse

Info on FLEXPART products for the webpage

- Upper left box selects **station code** that the user wants to view.
- Next two boxes on the right select **year** and **month** (2012-present).
- Then, the users select the product that he wants to view (Source Spec, Footprint, DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC, Total BC, Continental Spec, Age Spec).
- Final box on the right selects the **projection** (regional, global, polar).
- Buttons **FIRST**, **-10**, **PREV**, **NEXT**, **+10**, **LAST** navigate between different samples. For example, suppose we visualize product **Footprint** for station **ES0018G** for year **2020** and month **January** on 07-Jan-2020 at 18:00 to 21:00 (instance 55/248). The users navigate to the first footprint (01-Jan-2020 at 00:00 to 03:00) using the button **FIRST**, to the last footprint (31-Jan-2020 at 21:00 to 01-Feb-2020 at 00:00) with button **LAST**, to previous (07-Jan-2020 at 15:00 to 18:00) and next footprints (07-Jan-2020 at 21:00 to 08-Jan-2020 at 00:00) with buttons **PREV** and **NEXT**. With buttons **-10** and **+10**, the users can go ten timesteps backward (06-Jan-2020 at 12:00 to 15:00) or forward (09-Jan-2020 at 00:00 to 03:00) from the current timestep.
- Buttons **VIEW PLOT** and **NETCDF** (for map products) or **VIEW DATA** (for spectrum products) switch between plot visualization and links for download the data. Map products (Footprint, DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC, Total BC) are in gridded arrays and are given in netCDF format, while spectrum products (Source Spec, Continental Spec, Age Spec) are given in ascii format.

Explanation of products included in the webpage.

- **Footprint**: Footprint emissions sensitivity showing the probability of any release occurring in any grid-cell to reach the receptor (station) for 30 days particle tracking. In newer versions of the product, the average column trajectory of the footprint is plotted on each map as a function of the height of the plume center (gray colorbar on the right). Each colored circle represents each day backward in time from the release. In addition, there is a timeseries plot under the map showing the plume height versus time backward in time (black line) and on the right secondary axes, the percentage of particles in the planetary boundary layer (PBL) in magenta color and the percentage of particles in the stratosphere (STRA) in blue. Each circle represents days backward from the release date and time.
- **DOM BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from residential and commercial sector plotted on a map (three projections). DOM includes emissions from combustion in heating and cooking stoves and boilers in households and public and commercial buildings (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **ENE BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from energy production sector plotted on a map (three projections). ENE includes emissions from combustion processes in power plants and generators (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **IND BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from industrial combustion plotted on a map (three projections). IND includes emissions from industrial boilers and industrial production processes (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **FLR BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from gas flaring plotted on a map (three projections). FLR includes emissions from oil and gas facilities (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **SHP BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from shipping activities in in-land waters plotted on a map (three projections) (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **WST BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from waste treatment and disposal sector plotted on a map (three projections). WST resembles emissions from waste incineration and treatment (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **TRA BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from transportation sector plotted on a map (three projections). TRA includes emissions from all land-based transport of goods, animals and persons on road networks and off-road activities (ECLIPSEv6, Klimont et al., <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-8681-2017>).
- **Fire BC**: Modelled contribution to surface black carbon (BC) from open biomass burning (excluding agricultural fires) plotted on a map (three projections) (GFEDv4, Giglio et al., <https://doi.org/10.1002/jgrg.20042>).
- **Total BC**: The sum of the BC contributions.
- **Source Spec**: Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the contribution of each source (DOM BC, ENE BC, IND BC, FLR BC, SHP BC, WST BC, TRA BC, Fire BC) to surface BC.
- **Continent Spec**: Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the continental contribution (OCE: Ocean, GNL: Greenland, SA: South America, CA: Central America, NA: North America, AFR: Africa, EUR: Europe, RUS: Russia, ASI: Asia excluding Russian part, AUS: Australia) to surface BC.
- **Age Spec**: Timeseries plot of modelled concentrations in 3h resolution showing the age contribution of the plume to surface BC. The latter shows how "fresh" or "old" the air arriving at the receptor is.

Figure 22: Comprehensive documentation of the products, providing detailed descriptions of available products and parameters for selection on the "FLEXPART products" page for Black Carbon.

7.2 Statistics on use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. First it is the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, then the number of visits to the ACTRIS footprint analysis service itself (<https://flexpart-request.nilu.no/>) and lastly the number of FLEXPART requests, i.e. the request forms filled out with request for model runs at a given station/location.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
ACTRIS Footprint analysis service	Visits	Visits to web interface	IP-based
	Requests	FLEXPART model run requests via form	Tracked in Redmine

Table 11: Overview of usage metrics for ACTRIS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

7.2.1 Usage metrics for the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Use of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page is tracked using Matomo. The user map in Figure 23 shows the distribution of entries worldwide (1278 visits) and in Europe (1000 visits). Table 12 lists the countries with the most users of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page, and the number of visits made by each country. Lastly, Figure 24 shows the visits and actions (e.g., page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit over time.

Figure 23: User map showing on the left-hand side a total of 1278 visits to the ACTRIS Footprint Analysis Service web-page worldwide, and on the right-hand side 1000 visits in Europe during 15.05.2023 - 01.11.2024.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Norway	324
United States	167
France	115
Switzerland	94
Italy	71
Austria	61
Spain	54
Germany	53
Greece	41
United Kingdom	37

Table 12: Countries with the most users of the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page during 15.05.2023 - 01.11.2024.

Figure 24: Two graphs showing visits and actions per visit over time from 15.05.2023 - 01.11.2024. The upper graph shows both number of visits (in blue) and actions per visit (in orange), while the lower graph shows only actions per visit to properly see the scale. This gives an average of 2.2 actions (page views, downloads, outlinks and internal site searches) per visit.

7.2.2 Model requests in the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

The number of requests for the footprint analysis service is tracked in the Aeris Redmine issue tracker. Statistics on the requests can be found in Table 13. The ACTRIS footprint service started out with black carbon (BC) products, and has extended with other products such as dust, microplastics, NRT and more (other products) since the launch of the service. As this service is new within this project, many ACTRIS sites have asked for the standardized products such as BC and NRT which can explain the high demand.

Statistic	Number
Requests	95
Requests in progress	6
Completed issues	89

Stations with black carbon products for 10 years, 3h resolution (years 2012-2022)	21
Stations with dust products	9
Stations with specialized black carbon products	22
Stations with other products	6
Stations with microplastics products	21
Stations with NRT products	24

Table 13: Statistics on requests of the service via the FLEXPART request form on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service web-page until 01.12.2024.

7.3 Feedback from users on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Internal feedback
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in November 2024, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during December 2024 - January 2025.

7.3.1 User panel on the ACTRIS footprint analysis service

The second Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place on the 30th of April 2024. The discussion highlighted improvements in login functionality via ATMO-ACCESS. It was recommended to include clear guidance for users on acknowledging the project, including PIDs on downloadable results. While there is user interest in continuing the service beyond ATMO-ACCESS, securing funding remains a priority. Efforts to promote the service should persist through conferences, workshops, and scientific use case examples. Additionally, user guides should be made accessible via links on the initial ATMO-ACCESS virtual access page. The details of the responses are summarized in Milestone MS21 section on ACTRIS Footprint tool (aerosol & BC): <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content/aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/07/MS21-Feedback-meeting-2-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf>

7.3.2 Response on feedback form related to ACTRIS footprint analysis.

Figures 25 through 29 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the ACTRIS footprint analysis; however, it is important to note that the data in the figures is based on responses from only two users and therefore represents a limited perspective. In Figure 25, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses indicating "OK" to "Very satisfied" ratings across various aspects. Figure 26 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with high ratings provided. In Figure 27, the users indicated a preference for various training formats, with both users wishing for videos, e-

learning and interactive webinars. Figure 28 highlights the users' positive evaluation of the FLEXPART footprints, and Figure 29 outlines the perceived benefits, such as easy data access and immediate access to results. While these insights are valuable, they are limited in scope due to the two single responses.

Figure 25: Answers to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

Figure 26: Answers to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

Figure 27: Answers to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

Figure 28: Answers to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Figure 29: Answers to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

8 ICOS Footprint analysis service for greenhouse gases

The ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service allows users to explore greenhouse gas concentrations and footprints for ground-based stations in Europe.

The STILT results viewer (Figure 30) allows to select all footprint data available in the repository and to display an animation of the footprints together with the modelled CO₂ or CH₄ concentrations and contributions from different source categories. For ICOS stations and some selected other European stations, also the measured concentrations are included for comparison. The viewer also provides the option to download the model results.

The STILT calculation service allows users to interactively start new STILT model runs for any new location within the model domain (Figure 31).

STILT results viewer

Figure 30: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT results viewer page (link: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/viewer/>).

STILT calculation service Job starter

[STILT viewer](#) [Help](#)

Existing STILT stations

Start new STILT run

Site id (letter code + altitude) [Load data](#)

Site name

ICOS station id

Country code
— Select —

Latitude (decimal degree)

Longitude (decimal degree)

Altitude above ground (meters)

Start date (YYYY-MM-DD)

End date (YYYY-MM-DD)

[Submit STILT job](#)

Submitted STILT jobs

[Show details](#)

Job queue

- Site 'ERS040' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'FKL015' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'JAR110' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'KAS' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'KAT100' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)

Running computations

- Site 'CRP014' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)

Finished computations

- Site 'BIS047' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'MHD' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'CRA060' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BSD248' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BRM212' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'BIK300' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'HEI' (2023-01-01 - 2023-12-31)
- Site 'HEI' (2023-01-01 - 2023-01-01)

To keep our services free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring. Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and the development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

[Give us Feedback](#)

Legal mentions

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme through the ATMO-ACCESS Integrating Activity under grant agreement No 101008004.
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Figure 31: ATMO-ACCESS ICOS STILT calculation service page (link: <https://stilt.icos-cp.eu/worker/>).

8.1 Updates since last feedback report

Since the last report, several features were implemented based on user feedback:

- The calculation of CH₄ concentrations was implemented. All existing concentration results were updated in the repository with CH₄ concentrations in January 2024 and since then in each calculation CO₂ and CH₄ concentrations are calculated simultaneously.

- CO₂ and CH₄ observations from more stations in Europe, which are not part of ICOS but provided data for the European ObsPack compiled by ICOS, are now also included in the STILT results viewer for comparison with model results.
- Users can now pre-select whether they want to select from ICOS stations, existing European stations or all locations for which model results are available. This makes the search and selection of stations via the map or in the drop-down list much clearer.
- In the calculation service, users are now asked to provide not only a station ID but also a descriptive station name and the country in which the station is located. This enhances the reusability of the results for other users.
- User email addresses are now obscured in the calculation queue, showing only the first and last three characters.
- Navigation back and forth between the STILT viewer page and the calculation service was implemented.
- The documentation of model and input data provenance was updated and is available on the ICOS website without requiring login to ATMO-ACCESS.

8.2 Statistics on use of the ICOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the ICOS STILT station footprint calculation and viewing service are tracked through the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access Portal, recording the number of model runs started and result packages downloaded. The number of times the footprint animation was viewed on the ICOS STILT results viewer page is recorded since 22 March 2024.

The statistics are available since June 2023 until 1 November 2024.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
ICOS Footprint analysis service	Footprint animation/view	Footprint animation displayed in the STILT results viewer	Counter per display event; each view include up to one year of footprints
	Model run	STILT model runs started	1 run may cover multiple days
	Downloads	Model results downloaded	1 download may include multiple days
	Footprint day	Simulated footprint days generated	1 day = 8 footprints

Table 14: Overview of usage metrics for ICOS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

8.2.1 Usage Metrics for the ICOS Footprint Viewer

Figure 32 shows the number of times footprint animations were displayed on the ICOS STILT results viewer page. Each time a user selects a station and a year, all footprints and concentrations available for this time period are shown. The views are tracked separately since 22 March 2024.

8.2.2 Model requests for the ICOS Footprint Service

Figure 34 shows the number of model runs started since June 2023. Each model run applies to a single station, the requested time period can vary between a few days and several years (up to 18 years). In autumn, there is usually an increase in usage of the footprint calculation service as soon as the model runs for the previous year are opened. In 2024, this peak in usage extends into November due to a delay in the provision of input data and is therefore not fully covered in these statistics. In addition, there are always episodes when individual users start a large number of model runs for use in their projects.

Figure 34: Number of STILT model runs started in the ICOS footprint service between 14 June 2023 and 1 November 2024. The upper graph shows model run starts per week and the lower graph shows the cumulative sum of runs with a total of 1019 runs.

As each run can cover one or more days of footprints, we can also look at the number of footprint days. Each day calculated will produce eight 3-hourly footprints.

Figure 35: The monthly number of footprint days calculated in the GHG footprint tool

Over the period in total 73 individual users requested in 1019 calculations of 193664 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 1549312 calculated footprints.

8.2.3 Model results downloaded for the ICOS Footprint Service.

Figure 36 shows the number of model result packages downloaded since June 2023. Each package contains footprints and concentration time series for a single station and one year.

Figure 36: Number of downloads of packaged model results in the ICOS footprint service between 14 June 2023 and 1 November 2024. The upper graph shows downloads per week and the lower graph

shows the cumulative sum of package downloads with a total of 472 downloads. Note the maximum of 219 downloads in one single week of August 2024

As each download can cover one or more days of footprints, we can also look at the number of footprint days downloaded. Each day in the download archive will consist of eight 3-hourly footprints.

Figure 37: The monthly number of footprint days downloaded from the GHG footprint tool

Over the period in total 31 individual users requested through 472 download requests 208936 footprint days, which corresponds to in total 1671488 footprints.

8.3 Feedback from users on the ICOS footprint analysis

Feedback on the service is provided in several ways:

- Through user's panel meeting every six months
- Through the general feedback form

The end of the feedback period was in December 2024 and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account until January 2025.

8.3.1 User panel on the ICOS footprint analysis

The second feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in April 2024. In the meeting, users provided valuable feedback on further improvements of the user support, such as guidance on how to acknowledge the project and the services, traceability of results via PIDs, and adding scientific use case examples in the user guide. The user panel encouraged us to continue promoting the footprint service at conferences and workshops, possibly with hands-on sessions.

Details of the feedback is available in Milestone MS5.5 section 1.2: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/07/MS21-Feedback-meeting-2-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf>

8.3.2 Response on feedback form related to ICOS footprint analysis

Figures 38 through 42 provide an overview of user feedback and evaluations related to the ICOS footprint analysis; however, it is important to note that the data in the figures is based on responses from a single user and therefore represents only one individual's perspective. In Figure 38, the user rated the functionality and relevance of the service, with responses indicating "OK" to "Very satisfied" ratings across various aspects. Figure 39 reflects the user's willingness to recommend the service to a colleague, with a high rating provided. In Figure 40, the user indicated a preference for training resources such as e-learning tutorials and a library of resources. Figure 41 highlights the user's positive evaluation of the ICOS footprint analysis and Figure 42 outlines the perceived benefits, such as easy data access and immediate access to results. While these insights are valuable, they are limited in scope due to the single response.

Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used

Figure 38: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the functionality & relevance of the online service you used".

Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?

Figure 39: Answer to the question "Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague?".

Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

Figure 40: Answer to the question "Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?".

Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

Figure 41: Answer to the question "Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective".

Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Figure 42: Answer to the question "Shortly comment on the benefits of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt".

9 IAGOS Footprint analysis service for tropospheric vertical profiles

The IAGOS footprint analysis service combines the viewer of FLEXPART footprints and modelled SOFT-IO CO₂ contributions and allows users to explore tropospheric vertical profiles of carbon monoxide mixing ratios (measured by IAGOS) in conjunction with source attribution data (calculated using the SOFT-IO model). The vertical profiles are from airports visited by commercial aircrafts equipped with IAGOS' instrumentation. The SOFT-IO model is based on the coupling of FLEXPART backward footprint (with the receptor points located along the profile) with emission inventory databases. The service provides a visualization of the above-mentioned data via a simple, attractive user interface. Figure 43 shows the IAGOS footprints viewer page where users can select an airport and a date to visualize the footprints.

⁶ Source attribution using FlexparT and carbon monoxide emission inventories for In-situ Observation database, cf. Sauvage et al., 2017, doi.org/10.5194/acp-17-15271-2017

Figure 43: ATMO-ACCESS IAGOS footprints viewer Starting page (link: <https://permalink.aeris-data.fr/atmo-access-footprint>).

9.1 Updates since last feedback report

Since the last feedback report, numerous suggestions expressed in the user feedback were implemented and resulted in the service improvement:

- A detailed user guide is available. It makes a complete tour of the service's functionalities and features.
- The anthropogenic emission inventory database was upgraded from CEDS2 to CAMS-GLOB-ANT, resulting in more precise and up-to-date estimation of anthropogenic

contribution to observed CO anomalies (the latter is one of the dataset directly explorable via the service).

- A time range filter was added. It allows users to filter the airports which contain data (CO measured by IAGOS and CO contribution estimated by the SOFT-IO model) within a chosen range of dates.

9.2 Statistics on use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Statistics on the use of the IAGOS footprint analysis service are tracked in several ways. Firstly, via the number of accesses through the ATMO-ACCESS VA Portal, then via the number of users to the IAGOS footprint analysis web-service itself, and lastly via the number of requests through the service. The difference between accesses through the VA portal (as described in subsection 4.2.2) and visits to the webpage itself gives an indication of the number of people going directly to the webpage vs number of people routed through the VA portal. The statistics are available since June 2023 until November 1st, 2024.

Service	Metric label	Definition & counting rule	Notes / caveats
IAGOS Footprint analysis service	Unique visits	Unique IP visits to viewer	IP-based
	Requests	Footprints displayed in viewer	Counted per display event

Table 15: Overview of usage metrics IAGOS Footprint analysis service, including counting rules and limitations.

9.2.1 Usage metrics for the IAGOS footprint analysis service

The IAGOS footprint analysis usage can be gauged by the number of people accessing the service. Figure 44 shows the number of unique (one unique IP address per day) visits over time. The total number of unique visits is 433 (previously 325 in D10.1, +33%) for the period June 22, 2023, to November 1, 2024, where the high peak at around 26th of September most likely is when the first user panel was held.

Footprints service - Visits

Figure 44: Number of visits over time - IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023 to November 1, 2024.

9.2.2 Model visualization requests for the IAGOS footprint analysis service

The number of requests is the number of footprints displayed. Figure 45 shows the number of footprints displayed over time.

Footprints service - Requests

Figure 45: Number of footprints displayed over time – IAGOS Footprints viewer service from June 22, 2023, to November 1, 2024.

The total number of footprints displayed for the IAGOS footprints viewer is 8643 (previously 7,448 in D10.1, +16%) for the period June 22, 2023, to November 1, 2024.

9.3 Feedback from users on the IAGOS footprint analysis service

Feedback on the service is provided through the user's panel meeting every six months. The end of the feedback period was in November 2024, and suggestions and most feedback will be taken into account during December 2024 – January 2025. Additionally, no responses were submitted to the general feedback form regarding the IAGOS footprint analysis service during this feedback period.

9.3.1 User panel on the IAGOS footprint analysis

The first Feedback meeting with the User Panel of the footprint service took place in September 2023 and a second one in April 2024. General feedback was very positive about the main features of the service. The main feedback was to facilitate the user experience.

More details on the feedback are available in Milestone MS5.4 section 1.2: <https://wp1.aeris-data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2023/11/atmo-access-milestone-20-v2.1.pdf> and in Milestone MS5.5 section 'IAGOS Footprint Tool (vertical gradients)': <https://wp1.aeris->

data.fr/wp-content-aeris/uploads/sites/82/2024/07/MS21-Feedback-meeting-2-with-user-panel-discussion-of-updates.pdf.

10 Conclusion and next steps

This deliverable marks the conclusion of the second feedback period. The feedback gathered will be reviewed by the respective teams and implemented where applicable by the end of January 2025, and form the bases for the final deliverables:

- D10.3 Report on long-term strategy of VA activities and the new services in ATMO-ACCESS, taking into account the tools developed in WP5 and their best usage for science, management and outreach.
- D10.4: Report on the suitability of the different services modalities taking into account finances, outreach and scientific impact.

11 Appendix: General Feedback Form

Feedback questionnaire for users of ATMO-ACCESS online services

You have used free services available from this site: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access>. To keep them free for you, ATMO-ACCESS deeply values feedback from users. We hope you will spend a few minutes on this feedback schema to feed our requested usage monitoring.

Your opinions and feedback will help the ATMO-ACCESS team to understand what we're doing well and where we need to get better. The feedback will be used by the VA management and development team, in strategic decision and project coordination.

Note that you should complete this form separately for every service instance that you want to provide feedback on!

** indikerer at spørsmålet er obligatorisk*

1. Privacy notice *

The ATMO-ACCESS privacy notice can be accessed at this link: <https://www.atmo-access.eu/atmo-access-privacy-policy/>

All replies will be treated in the strictest confidence. The information given will only be used for monitoring and assessment purposes in accordance with the European [General Data Protection Regulation](#).

Merk av for alt som passer

I agree with the ATMO-ACCESS privacy policy and terms of use

2. Do you agree to be contacted for further feedback or to be informed of further improvements? (If yes, please add your email address below!) *

Merk av for alt som passer

Yes

No

3. Email address

4. First name

5. Last name

6. Home institution

7. Your background and position *

Check all that apply.

Merk av for alt som passer

- Academic (post-doc, researcher, lecturer)
- Student (undergraduate, PhD)
- Project leader
- Air quality network and/or other Research Infrastructure
- Industry
- Private enterprise
- Government Organisation
- Independent Scientist
- Andre: _____

8. How did you find out about the online services supported within the ATMO-ACCESS project? *

Merk av for alt som passer

- ATMO-ACCESS website
- Research infrastructure websites
- Direct mailing from Research Infrastructure
- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Other social media
- Information recieved by colleagues/personal contacts
- Information recieved at event
- Andre: _____

9. Service accessed *

If you have tried more than one of these, please complete the entire form once for each service you want to give feedback on.

Markér bare én oval.

- Homeless Data Portal
- Footprint - Aerosol distribution and source analysis
- Footprint - Greenhouse gases
- Footprint - Tropospheric vertical gradients
- Time Series Analysis
- MOOC - Massive Open Online Courses
- Helpdesk for any of the services

10. Please evaluate the **access** to the online services from <https://www.atmo-access.eu/virtual-access> *

Markér bare én oval per rad

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Publicity and information on the access portal before login	<input type="radio"/>				
System for registration and authentication to get access to the service	<input type="radio"/>				
Publicity and information on the access portal after login	<input type="radio"/>				

11. Please evaluate the **functionality & relevance** of the online service you used

*

Markér bare én oval per rad

	Not relevant	Poor	OK	Satisfied	Very satisfied
Information about the service offered	<input type="radio"/>				
Interaction with and support by the virtual access service provider(s) (scientific and technical support)	<input type="radio"/>				
Interpretation and understanding of the outcome and results	<input type="radio"/>				
Did the service comply with your expectations?	<input type="radio"/>				

12. Would you recommend the service you used to a colleague? *
This mainly concerns the scientific usefulness

Markér bare én oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Def. Certainly!

13. Which of these training resources do you think would be good to have in order for people to make the best use of the service?

Merk av for alt som passer

- Videos
- e-learning tutorials (with examples)
- Interactive webinars
- In-person training (e.g. at conferences)
- Library of scientific use cases
- Written documentation
- Andre: _____

14. Please feel free to share any other comments/suggestions about the service you used!

15. Please evaluate the service provided by the ATMO-ACCESS Virtual Access activity, from your perspective

*

This covers both the access process and the online services

Markér bare én oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Ver: Excellent

16. If your evaluation is ≤ 2 , we appreciate if you can briefly explain why:

17. Shortly comment on the **benefits** of the Virtual Access and/or lessons learnt

Merk av for alt som passer

- Saving time
 Scientific and technical support
 Easy data access
 Immediate access to the results / interactive analysis
 Ready-to-use graphics
 Andre: _____

18. Do you have any further comments/suggestions about the Virtual Access setup?

12 Appendix: Homeless Data Portal - Frequently Asked Questions

What does “homeless data” refer to and who can use this service?

In the ATMO-ACCESS Project “homeless data” refers to data sets not associated with any long-term projects nor sustainable data centres. This includes data sets from Transnational Access (TNA) activities, research campaigns and ‘short-term’ national or international research projects.

Anyone with data which falls under the classification of “homeless data”, as described above, can use the service.

Is the service free of charge?

Data curation through the ATMO-ACCESS project is free of charge to the end of the project 1st of April 2025. Curation of homeless data will also be available after the projects end, but then associated to a low cost

Will my data be associated with the term “homeless data”?

The term “homeless data” itself is only used for the portal. All data curated through the ATMO-ACCESS homeless data portal will have an “ATMO-ACCESS” tag in the data centre for the respective RIs, to be able to identify these data later. Furthermore, the data can have additional tags, associating the data to a corresponding research project selected by the user of the service.

Can I request curation for stations, instruments or methods not already in the RIs?

Yes, if it's atmospheric measurement data.

What to expect from us after submitting a request?

After submitting a request, you will be contacted by a data curator from a relevant RI about the future process. The data curator will explain the workflow at the relevant RI and guide you through the process. You will get access to tools used for data curation/submission. After submitting the data in the right format with as much metadata as possible, the data will follow the standard workflow of the RI, including quality control tests. The RI will then make the data available for end-users and assign the data set(s) DOI(s) and give you access to usage tracking tools.

What is expected by me?

It is expected that you format your data according to the needs of the relevant RI, with guidance from the data curators, and provide metadata to accompany your data set.

Which research infrastructure (RI) should I expect to be contacted by?

ACTRIS for data on reactive trace gases, cloud and aerosol particle properties.

ICOS for surface data on greenhouse gases including halocarbons.

IAGOS for data collected on moving platforms (aircraft, drones, balloons).

Are there any tools for formatting the data correctly?

Yes, you will get access to RI specific tools for data curation after requesting data and being assigned to your relevant RI(s).

What benefits are there to using the Homeless Data Portal, compared to storing the data by myself?

Storing your data in a RIs is the most efficient way to ensure long term storage of your data and promote visibility and access data for a larger research community. Using the homeless data portal makes sure these data are well documented for future use and easily available. Furthermore, you as a data provider can get access to usage tracking of your data.

Will I get DOI(s) for my data set(s) and what is a collection DOI?

A DOI is a digital identifier of an object, any object — physical, digital, or abstract. When delivering data sets through the Homeless Data Portal, each data set will be provided with a DOI by the RI. If there are several data sets, for example across different RIs, we also provide the option to get a collection DOI. A collection DOI is thus one DOI that identifies a group or collection of data that e.g. might have data across the RIs.